

Case Study

Elmer, the army officer in Peru©

Andrew Hague

Department of Advanced Medicine. International Academy of Medical Sciences

*Corresponding author

Andrew Hague. Department of Advanced Medicine. International Academy of Medical Sciences.

Received: 18 Aug 2023

Accepted : 21 Aug 2023

Published: 25 Apr 2023

Copyright

© 2023 Andrew Hague

OPEN ACCESS

Abstract

Gangrene is always considered untreatable and can only be stopped by amputation. Often the surgery fails to remove all the infection and more of the limb has to be cut off. This is a report about stopping gangrene with a non-invasive treatment taking only a few minutes and not using any drugs.

What happened

Elmer was leading soldiers in the jungle of Peru when a landmine exploded injuring his legs. By the time he got to hospital, gangrene had set in. He was eight years in hospital suffering repeated amputations. The doctors were unable to stop the infection so they removed his legs bit by bit until there was nothing left to remove. That was when the CellSonic doctor, Dr Dario Rodriguez dariore@gmail.com, heard about the plight and was invited to treat the officer. He applied one treatment as shown in the photograph. All the infection was stopped.

At last Elmer could return home. The video of the presentation at the military heroes' association shows Elmer now fit and well in a wheel chair. In a touching scene, he receives a kiss from his wife. CellSonic saved his life.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BJ9Qd1eUrlA&spfreload=10>

The cure

The prime force for killing infection is pressure. CellSonic emits very intense pressure pulses (VIPP) four times a second that kill viruses, bacteria and parasites. It is not necessary to know what the germs are or exactly where they are. Treat all the area and beyond to catch everything. More oxygen is sent in the blood to the site. Vascularisation is increased. Nitric oxide is increased. Stem cells of the right type in the right quantity are sent to exactly the right location under instructions from the immune system alerted by the CellSonic VIPP. New skin is grown embedded with nerves. Nerves that served the severed limbs are re-programmed to stop phantom pain. All this happens within the CellSonic treatment. No drugs are used and there are no side effects.

Elmer being treated for gangrene

Doctors

Lima military hospital. Dr Rodriguez is on the left

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BJ9QdIeUrlA&spfreload=10>

References

1. Full information about CellSonic VIPP is given at [CellSonic Medical \(cellsonic-medical.com\)](http://cellsonic-medical.com)
2. Wound healing is under Applications at [CellSonic Medical \(cellsonic-medical.com\)](http://cellsonic-medical.com)
3. Another case study of gangrene is at [Tragic tale of successful cure. pdf \(cellsonic-medical.com\)](http://cellsonic-medical.com)

Elmer gets a kiss from his wife.
Elmer, Lima, Peru

Cite this article: Andrew Hague (2023). Elmer, the army officer in Peru©. *International Journal of Surgery and Health Care*, (4): 27-28.

Copyright: ©2023 **Andrew Hague**. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.